

**BUILDING FINANCIAL DASHBOARD TOWARDS BETTER MANAGEMENT OF
PROFITABILITY FOR BANKS AND NON-BANK FINANCIAL ORGANIZATIONS**

MSc Dissertation

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University of
South Wales
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**FACULTY OF COMPUTING, ENGINEERING, AND SCIENCE
UNIVERSITY OF SOUTH WALES, UNITED KINGDOM**

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MSc Dissertation

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The MSc dissertation is submitted to the faculty of Computing, Engineering, and Science
The University of South Wales, the United Kingdom in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the
master's degree in Computing and Information Systems.

Declaration

I hereby declare that this project titled “Building Financial Dashboard towards better management of profitability for Banks and Non-Banks financial organization”, entirely is my own work and that, to the best of my knowledge and belief, it contains no material previously published or written by another person nor material which has been accepted for the award of any other degree or diploma of the university or other institute of higher learning, except where due acknowledgment has been made in the text. The work I have presented does not breach any existing copyright and no portion of this report has been copied from any work done earlier for a degree or otherwise.

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Abstract

Banking industry and non-bank financial organizations are matured to a great extent than in earlier periods. It has developed a tremendous image in its various activities including using the core banking system software. Now advanced banking technologies have been launched in each area of banking operations. Like many other developing countries, Bangladesh is not lagged behind in using core banking system software for daily banking operations. Banks and non-bank financial organizations of Bangladesh presently use different web-based core banking system software and other account management tools for storing daily business transactions. But analyzing different core banking software and other account management tools, it comes to the observation that, the existing systems used in financial sectors are transactional only. Those system features are not analytical somehow. The managers and top management of the organizations are not benefited from the systems for making analytical decisions.

Considering the scenarios, building a financial dashboard for managers and top management of Banks and non-bank financial organizations is one of the most demanded and latest features in the banking sector of Bangladesh for better management of profitability.

This paper tried to unearth the present status, prospects, and future challenges of using a financial dashboard in the banking sector of Bangladesh and demonstrate the building process of a web-based financial dashboard. Considering the importance of the financial dashboard this study was taken up. The main aim of this study was to build a web-based financial dashboard to facilitate the managers and top management of banks and non-bank financial organizations for making analytical decisions with the help of the dashboard. The major objectives of this study were to evaluate the present conditions of the existing core banking system software and other account management tools used in the financial sector of Bangladesh and identify the drawbacks and provide probable solutions with the help of a financial dashboard. The study found large expansion attempts in core banking system software in the banking industry of Bangladesh where analytical tools and features are ignored. The importance of financial dashboards is not taken into consideration. By the dashboard, managers and top management of the organization can make the right decision at the right time and can increase profitability and prohibit the incurred loss for making the wrong decision. The private commercial and foreign commercial banks have been performing well than those state-owned commercial banks regarding core banking system software in Bangladesh. Based on the study, it can be stated that the banking industry of Bangladesh is moving forward to the age of automation of banking activities with the help of advanced technological facilities.

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CHAPTER ONE

Introduction

1.1 Introduction

This thesis paper has tried to discover the present status, prospects, and future challenges of using a financial dashboard in the banking sector of Bangladesh and demonstrated the building process of a web-based financial dashboard. Considering the importance of the financial dashboard to facilitate the managers and top management of banks and non-bank financial organizations for making analytical decisions with the help of the dashboard a web-based multi-featured dashboard has been developed where probable solutions to different analytical problems have been provided.

However, mostly the issues of commercial banking in Bangladesh have been considered rather than others. The research has been conducted based on secondary data that are available online and, in some journals, and magazines as well as some organization personnel have been interviewed.

1.2 Background of the Study

Banks and non-bank financial organizations play a vital role in the economy of every country in the world. The predominantly Banking sector is the backbone of the economy. That's why study and development in this field are highly demanding and challenging as well. Besides this is a personal area of interest to study and develop in this field as a banker.

In Bangladesh, the Banking industry is more developed than in the earlier period. It has developed diverse values in its various activities including the use of core banking system software. The web-based core banking system is one of the most demanded and latest technologies used in the banking sector. Nevertheless, the limitations of the core banking system are sometimes monotonous and most of the core banking system software and other account management tools are transactional where analytical features are ignored in every aspect of Bangladesh excluding some private and multinational banks. Now the main challenge of this sector is to develop a useful analytical featured financial dashboard. In addition, nowadays the managers and top management of the banking industries are demanding more featured and reliable web-based financial dashboards and they can make the decision as quickly as possible with the help of financial dashboards and overcome the undesired situation in the quickest possible time.

1.3 Statement of Problem

In the edge of ICT (Information & Communication Technology), using banking software has great importance in modern banking. Banking software enables bankers to provide advanced banking services. The banking industry of Bangladesh has already used to the core banking system to cope

with the developed countries. However, the analytical features and other limitations of the core banking system and account management tools are the legs behind making the right decision for the managers and top management of the bank. Even the banking software presently used in the banking industries in Bangladesh is mostly transactional and not analytical at all. Most banks are looking for analytical solution base banking software to overcome this situation and ensure modern banking and that is the main challenge for the banking industry of Bangladesh towards better management of profitability. There are very small numbers of studies conducted in this respect to identify the factors.

1.4 Problem Definition

In the past, managers and top management of the bank were making decisions by analyzing problems manually, and sometimes they took the wrong decision because of the non-availability of analytical information. However, the present-day managers and top management are really struggling with analytical information to identify what the real problems are, and which indicators are creating barriers to achieving the desired profit. Which operational activities should be reduced and where should be focused on? Thus, the study seeks to investigate the impact of the analytical dashboard on the banking sector of Bangladesh. Further, the study investigated the present status, prospects, and challenges of implementing the financial dashboard in the banking industry of Bangladesh.

1.5 Research Question

The main research question is as follows:

How can the manager and top management of the banking industry of Bangladesh make the right decision with the help of a financial indicator analysis dashboard and handle the other challenges inherent to achieving desired profit?

To satisfy this question through this study, some other sub-questions also arise. Those sub-questions are:

- What is the present condition and prospects of core banking software in Bangladesh?
- What are the major challenges inherent in implementing a financial dashboard in Bangladesh?

- How can improve the core banking system software to determine the problems and get probable solutions by analyzing various financial indicators, and ratios which has a direct impact on profitability?

1.6 The main aim of the Project

The main aim of this study was to build a web-based financial analytical dashboard by analyzing different financial indicators, ratios, and the other matrix which influenced predominantly profitability, to facilitate the managers and top management of banks and non-bank financial organizations for making the right and effective decision at the quickest possible time with the help of the web-based financial analytical dashboard.

1.7 Objective of the Study

The major objective of this study is to investigate the existing features of the present core banking system software used in the banking industry of Bangladesh and its present status, prospects, and challenges. The other specific objectives of the study are-

Analysis - Evaluate the present conditions of the existing core banking system software and other account management tools used in the financial sector of Bangladesh and identify the drawbacks inherent in existing core banking system software in Bangladesh by analyzing a detailed literature review.

Design – Design a web framework-based financial analytical dashboard. Using Unified Modeling Language (UML) and Entity Relationship Diagram (ERD), design an appropriate diagram that is necessary to build the application.

Implementation – Build a web-based financial analytical dashboard application using Python where Django is to be used for creating the web framework and SQLite3 to be used in the back-end database. Matplotlib, Folium, NumPy, and other required libraries to be used to analyze significant financial indicators, and ratios and visualize the information on the dashboard. Finally, deploy the system and host the web application using Hiroku free web trial hosting site, and Git version control system for live trial.

Evaluation – Evaluate the system and get feedback from the expert in the financial domain about usability, effectiveness, etc. In the feedback section of the web application through team interviews.

1.8 Structure of the Dissertation

The below structure has been followed for performing the whole research process.

Chapter-2: Literature review: In this chapter, it has focused on some literature that has been studied and analyzed to find the gap for further study related to the subject matter of the research. That means some studies about core banking system software and its existing features which are currently used in the banking sector of Bangladesh are searched and analyzed to get findings and then decides to go for further study. Several findings have been captured from different articles and other sources to precede this research.

Chapter-3: Organizational Overview: In this chapter, the overviews of the selected banks and other non-bank financial organizations are presented. The present operational activities, existing tools, and techniques used for managing transactional operations and other activities of the banks and non-bank financial organizations are described in this part of the paper.

Chapters 4-6: Dashboard Design, Implement, and Evaluation: In these three chapters the collected data are analyzed to identify the requirements of the dashboard, and the entire web-based financial dashboard design, implementation, and evaluation process have been discussed. However, most of the data are collected from secondary sources and some organizational personnel has been interviewed as primary data sources.

Chapter-7: Findings, Conclusion, and Recommendations: In this chapter, the research provides a summary of the research which means a gist of research findings. This part reflects the research objectives and questions and portrays remarks for the readers where recommendations are the outcomes of those objectives that direct the readers on what would be most appropriate regarding the subject matter.

1.9 Conclusion

This is the introductory part where the researcher showed the background, rationale, and significance of the study. The aims and objectives are covered and developed researcher questions that are to be answered. The research area and aims are addressed in this chapter and several questions are determined to answer through this study. Furthermore, a good research structure is generated and shown in this part. However, based on this chapter, the researcher is directed for performing the next parts of the research so that all parts are to be completed in a logical and ethical manner.

CHAPTER TWO

Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

It is a common phenomenon to refer briefly to the previous studies and research in the related areas of the subject to find out and fill up the research gaps if any. This chapter presents a review of previous studies related to the present study. The chapter constitutes an examination of studies related to the impact of using a financial analytical dashboard on profitability in banking the industry of Bangladesh and some other countries to some extent. The research tried to find out the existing gap or scope from those previous studies for the present study.

2.2 Literature Review

In the view of the research by Janes, Sillitti, and Succi in 2013, in the 19th century, the term “dashboard” was used to refer to a board in front of a carriage that stopped mud from being splashed (dashed) into the vehicle by the horse’s hooves. Later, cars began using dashboards to inform the driver about the status of the car’s various functions. When a problem arises, the colors of the dashboard indicators show how urgent the situation is. As per the publication of the Visual Business Intelligence Newsletter of Perceptual Edge, the dashboard is a visual display of the most important information needed to achieve one or more objectives, consolidated, and arranged on a single screen so the information can be monitored briefly (Few, 2006). Eckerson said in his book Performance Dashboard in 2010 that, Dashboards were initially created for the automobile sector; however, they have recently been adopted by various organizations and institutions, such as banks. The trend of adoption started with the bank employees’ idea of having an “executive dashboard” that helps them to drive their company. In addition, there is a growing need to increase profits by meeting the needs of demanding customers. Therefore, executives improve quality and cut costs of their organization, but these are short-term efforts, so they propose to use a ‘Financial Analytics Dashboard’ which will help them achieve their long-term strategic goals in the most effective manner (Eckerson, 2010). The Dashboard is an online and interactive central repository of disclosure data that is can be updated frequently or on the day end or monthly or quarterly in any instance. It is a tool to enhance the effectiveness of prudential disclosures of financial stability and efficiency (Bis.org, 2022). A financial dashboard is a business intelligence tool that enables finance and accounting teams to visualize, track, and report financial KPIs. Modern dashboards go beyond general visualization and reporting through the convenience of financial analysis to synthesize disparate financial and accounting data and allow analysts to drill deeper into data and gain insights that will reduce costs and improve profitability (12 Financial Dashboard Examples & Templates, 2022). The financial

dashboard provides instance reports about the performance of the establishment against the specified KPIs. A financial dashboard provides banks with full control over their daily business operations (How to Create Financial Analytics Dashboards for BFSI Firms, 2022). A banking business intelligence dashboard is an analytical display tool that's linked to different banking data sets across multiple systems. Those systems include but are not limited to: the bank's core banking platform, CRMs, loan-processing software, and any other type of banking data warehouse (Top 3 Banking Dashboard Examples for Business Intelligence - OpsDog, 2022). Financial Data analytics has become an obvious part and parcel of many industries. The finance sector is no exception. Banks use analytics to identify the drawbacks, understand customer transaction patterns, and trace market trends for financial products and services. It helps understand and identify individual customer needs such as loans, insurance policies, and investments. Keeping up with current trends gives the bank an advantage over its competitors. There are more opportunities to grab and become successful. Banks and financial institutions have largely benefitted from using data financial analytics (How to Create Financial Analytics Dashboards for BFSI Firms, 2022). Banking dashboards are used to visually track and display banking KPIs (those are key performance indicators; more on them in a minute). They also track banking business process results, customer trends, financial performance pretty much anything you want to track, so long as you've got the data to crunch. (Top 3 Banking Dashboard Examples for Business Intelligence - OpsDog, 2022). One of the solutions with the right approach is creating a smart Business Intelligence system that comes in BI Dashboard. By highlighting the key performance and indicators of transactional data, managers are expected to gain information or insights that can be used as a reference to give more accurate promotions. Finally, cluster analysis using the K-Means algorithm is also provided to group data against its respective characteristics that may have been unnoticed. Then, stakeholders can translate the characteristics of each cluster into their business perspective. Based on the test results by comparing two samples from the pretest and posttest results (paired T-Test), the knowledge value of the management team after implementing the BI Dashboard increased to 95.2%. Therefore, the BI Dashboard with the K-Means algorithm is a suitable method to be applied as a decision making for e-banking product promo recommendations for payment and purchase transactions (Ady Buananta & Chowanda, 2021).

2.3 Ideal Characteristics of Financial Dashboard

A financial analytics dashboard is a tool that displays the performance of an organization using various indicators and it breaks the organization's strategy into objectives, metrics, initiatives, and tasks that are tailored for each unit in the organization. It allows people to monitor, measure, and manage the key activities and processes needed to achieve the goals of the organization. It should

have some good characteristics to become an effective financial dashboard. Different from the financial dashboard, an analytical reporting system is a simple system designed to report some key performance indicators of the organization. It may not be well designed to achieve the goals of the organization. After reviewing journals from sources such as ScienceDirect, Scopus, and Google Scholar it has been considered that an ideal financial dashboard should have the following characteristics: The financial analytical dashboard should allow people to monitor, measure, and manage the key activities and processes needed to achieve the goals set. The sequence of the functions is to monitor, measure, and then manage (Eckerson, 2010; Van Grembergen & Amelinckx, 2002), which is briefly explained as follows:

1. **Monitor** is a function for monitoring crucial business processes and activities by tracking the business performance metrics or indicators. If the business performance is in a danger zone, an alarm will be triggered to inform the authorities about the problem. After a problem is reported, it will be measured or analyzed.

2. **Measure** is a function for determining the root causes of problems by focusing on relevant and timely information from multiple perspectives and at various levels of detail. The analytical the function is usually supported by a drilling-down mechanism that allows the users to explore the activities in the performance dashboard at each level of the organization and analyze each indicator in the dashboard in detail. For example, the decline of the organization's net profit can be drilled down to each individual business unit, and net profit can be analyzed further into revenue and cost. Once the causes of the problems are found, the problems will be managed and solved.

3. **Manage** is a function that enables people and processes to improve decisions, optimize performance, and steer the organization in the right direction after the root causes of problems are found and corrected.

2.4 Key Performance Indicators of Banking Dashboard

There are predominantly 17 key performance indicators that every bank should track. For large financial institutions and small, local banks alike, these KPIs provide important insights into everything from finances to operations. A multitude of KPIs can be implemented to measure every type of transaction and service in a bank to accurately evaluate performance, profit, customer service, and more. It can be hard to choose which measures to focus on. These metrics are applicable to banks of all sizes and cover the most important aspects of operations and management. These

metrics provide important insights into how the bank and its employees perform, and what's contributing to the profit and what's not, so it is helpful to make strategic decisions on everything from hiring to resource allocation. Ultimately, KPIs evaluate the success of the bank and quantify its performance in tangible ways for the leadership and stakeholders (Lucco, Smith, Jessee, and Jackson, 2022). here's a list of bank KPIs that should track, organized by category:

1. **Revenue:** All incoming cash flow. Banks might break down the total revenue by deposit interest, loan interest, service fees, and transaction fees.
2. **Expenses:** All costs incurred during bank operations. Expenses are usually tracked separately in two categories: interest and noninterest.
3. **Operating Profit:** Money earned from core business operations, excluding deductions of interest and taxes. In its simplest form, this figure is obtained by subtracting expenses from revenue.
4. **Operating Expenses as a Percentage of Assets:** Total operating expenses divided by the total amount of owned assets, shown as a percentage.
5. **Assets Under Management:** The total value of assets being managed by the bank. This KPI can be tracked by various accounting timeframes, such as quarterly.
6. **Percentage of Asset above Benchmark:** How the bank's Asset ranks compared to competitors, shown as a percentage. This banking KPI helps evaluate the performance in the industry.
7. **Return on Equity:** Total income the bank generates is divided by the total equity owned by shareholders, shown as a percentage.
8. **Return on Assets (ROA):** The total dollar amount of net income generated by the bank divided by the total assets, shown as a percentage.
9. **Client Survey Score:** Bank performance as measured by customer feedback. Many banks send out client surveys to gather performance-related feedback; tracking these responses with some type of internal scorecard is helpful. It can even create categories for response types (e.g. employee communication, variety of products/offers, speed of service, etc.) and track them individually, as well as the overall customer satisfaction score.
10. **Average Time to Close Issues:** Length of time from when a problem is identified to when it is solved. Issues may originate internally (operations, technology, etc.) or externally (customers).

11. **New Account Setup Error Rate:** The total number of new customer accounts created containing an error (e.g. typo or incorrect address, name, account type, etc.) divided by the total number of new customer accounts set up at the same point in time, shown as a percentage. This metric will ultimately link to the previous “Average Time to Close Issues” KPI.
12. **Accounts Opened with Insufficient Documentation:** The total number of new accounts opened with insufficient documentation is divided by the total number of new accounts opened over the same period of time, shown as a percentage. This is similar to the previous KPI for banks, but in this case, the information is missing versus incorrect.
13. **Total Volume of Accounts:** The total number of accounts managed by your bank, tracked by financial timeframes. There are many types of accounts you can track, such as deposit or money market accounts.
14. **Asset per Employee:** The total value of assets being managed by the bank divided by the number of employees. This is an HR-related measure that helps analyze workload.
15. **Operating Profit per Employee:** The total amount of operating profits divided by the total number of employees. This is a high-level bank KPI that, in the simplest sense, helps you compare money earned to money spent on staff.
16. **Sales per Branch:** The total amount of sales generated through a single branch divided by the total number of branch locations. This KPI helps management assess which branches are the highest- and lowest-performing.
17. **Number of Workflow Processes Implemented:** Counting the processes that the bank has created or revised to improve workflows and better operations. This metric takes a more introspective approach to KPI tracking.

2.5 Present status of Financial Dashboard in Bank of Bangladesh

The banking sector in Bangladesh consists of several types of institutions. Bangladesh Bank is the central bank of Bangladesh and the chief regulatory authority in the banking sector. Pursuant to Bangladesh Bank Order, 1972 the Government of Bangladesh reorganized the Dhaka branch of the State Bank of Pakistan as the central bank of the country and named it Bangladesh Bank with retrospective effect from 16 December 1971. Other than the Central Bank itself, banks in Bangladesh are primarily categorized into two types: Scheduled and Non-Scheduled banks. Scheduled banks are licensed under the Bank Company Act, 1991 (Amended up to 2013). Currently,

there are 61 scheduled banks in Bangladesh (List of banks in Bangladesh - Wikipedia, 2022). Banking and financial sectors all around the world have embraced ICT To facilitate their customers with efficient services and innovative products through multichannel. The central engine that runs the core operations of the banking and financial institution is the Core Banking Software (CBS). The operational efficiency of a bank largely depends on the CBS. Moreover, it determines what a bank can offer in the future. In Bangladesh, ICT embracement has got momentum in the last decade. Some first-mover banks in Bangladesh are in the process of CBS up-gradation, and some other banks are trying to implement CBS to improve competitiveness, operational efficiency, and regulatory compliance. However, CBS implementation has challenges; improper attention to these challenges may result in poor CBS performance (Rahman, 2016). Depending on the importance of CBS the central bank of Bangladesh issued circular and guidelines in 2016 for all scheduled banks of Bangladesh for implementing CBS in managing transactional activities. Although the initiatives of implementing the CBS in the banking sector are appreciated, there are numerous limitations that still need to be overcome. The CBS presently used in the Banking industries of Bangladesh are predominantly transactional. Some banks are trying to build Financial analytics Dashboard but those are not providing critical analytical financial information to the managers and top management of the bank to make the necessary decision. So that this is a high demand to build financial analytics dashboards for the betterment of bank and non-bank financial organizations.

2.6 Conclusion

From the previously mentioned literature review, it is evident by many renowned researchers, science journals, different websites that, in the 19th century, the term “dashboard” was being used to refer to a board in front of a carriage that stopped mud from being splashed. Dashboards were initially developed for the automobile industry; however, they have recently been adopted by various organizations and institutions, such as banks. Dashboard is a visual display of the most important information needed to achieve one or more objectives. Financial Data analytics has become an obvious part and parcel of many industries. The finance sector is no exception. Banks use analytics to identify the drawbacks, understand customer transaction patterns, and trace market trends for financial products and services. It helps understand and identify individual customer needs such as loans, insurance policies, and investments. Keeping up with current trends gives the bank an advantage over its competitors. By the detail literature review, it is assumed that financial analytics dashboard plays vital role in the finance sector of many developed countries towards managing their profitability. On the other hand, it is being observed by researching many journal papers and interviewing by organizations personnel’s that, almost every organization of financial sectors are

used to in core banking system software for their daily transactional operations. But the software they are currently using are poor featured and don't have the financial analytical feature. However financial analytics dashboard can act as a complementary towards banking sector in Bangladesh. Financial analytic dashboard can help to increase profit and reduced the incurred losses by making right decision at the right time. So, the research identified that, there is a scope of building financial analytics dashboard towards better management of profitability in the banking sector of Bangladesh. Moreover, there are no significant research found on the impact of using financial analytics dashboard on the banking sector of Bangladesh. That's why assuming the importance of financial analytics dashboard for banks and non-bank bank financial institutions of Bangladesh a well-defined web-based financial analytics dashboard must be built toward better management of profitability of banking sector of Bangladesh.

CHAPTER THREE

Organizational Overview

3.1 Introduction

There are sixty-one commercial banks operating in Bangladesh. Among them most of them, using CBS (Core Banking System) software to provide services to the customers. Using of CBS is the regulatory requirements of central bank of Bangladesh. Besides providing services to the customers, they use CBS for their organizational purpose. Most banks developed their CBS by the local vendor and some of them have engaged their internal IT team to developed CBS. However, for ease of action, some of the banks have been selected for conducting this study. An overview of the selected banks is given in the following section.

3.2 Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited

Dutch-Bangla Bank started operation as Bangladesh's first joint venture bank. Dutch Bangla Bank was the first bank in Bangladesh to be fully automated. The Electronic-Banking Division was established in 2002 to undertake rapid automation and bring modern banking services into this field. Full automation was completed in 2003 and hereby introduced plastic money to the Bangladeshi masses. Dutch Bangla Bank also operates the nation's largest ATM fleet.

Name of the Company	Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited
Company Type	Private Limited Company
Head Office	Sena Kalyan Bhaban, 4th Floor, 195-Motijheel Commercial Area Dhaka-1000, Bangladesh.
SWIFT	DBBLBDDH
Website	www.dutchbanglabank.com
CBS Status	Fully functional
Financial Dashboard Status	Used but not fully analytics featured
Person interviewed	Mr. Mashrur Arefin Senior Executive Office, Duch-Bangla Bank Limited, Bagerhat, Bangladesh

Source: (Adapted from the website of Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited, Accessed on 20.08.2022)

3.3 Prime Bank Limited

Prime Bank Limited is a private commercial bank in Bangladesh. Prime Bank Limited runs its business with 145 branches across the country. Prime Bank offers all kinds of Commercial Corporate and Personal Banking services covering all segments of society within the framework of the Banking Company Act and regulations laid down by our central bank.

Name of the Company	Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited
Company Type	Private Limited Company
Head Office	Adamjee Court Annex Building-2, 119-120, Motijheel C/A, Dhaka-1000, Bangladesh.
SWIFT	PRBLBDDH
Website	www.primebank.com.bd
CBS Status	Fully functional
Financial Dashboard Status	Used but not fully featured
Person interviewed	

Source: (Adapted from the website of Prime Bank Limited, Accessed on 20.08.2022)

3.4 Islami Bank Bangladesh Limited

Islami Bank Bangladesh Limited is a Joint Venture Public Limited Company engaged in commercial banking business based on Islamic Shari'ah with 63.09% foreign shareholding having the largest branch network (total of 366 Branches) among the private sector Banks in Bangladesh. It is the pioneer of Islamic banking in Bangladesh.

Name of the Company	Islami Bank Bangladesh Limited
Company Type	Private Limited Company
Head Office	Islami Bank Tower 40, Dilkusha Commercial Area, Dhaka-1000, Bangladesh.

SWIFT	IBBLBDDH
Website	www.islamibankbd.com
CBS Status	Fully functional
Financial Dashboard Status	Used but not fully featured
Person interviewed	

Source: (Adapted from the website of Islami Bank Limited, Accessed on 20.08.2022).

3.5 Al-Arafah Islami Bank Limited

Al-Arafah Islami Bank Limited is an Islamic bank in Bangladesh. Al-Arafah Islami Bank Limited is a Sharia-compliant bank in Bangladesh founded on 27 September 1995. A Sharia council of the bank is responsible for ensuring the bank activities meet Sharia requirements.

Name of the Company	Al-Arafah Islami Bank Limited
Company Type	Private Limited Company
Head Office	36, Dilkusha (6-9 Floor) C/A, Dhaka-1000, Bangladesh.
SWIFT	ALARBDDH
Website	www.al-arafahbank.com
CBS Status	Fully functional
Financial Dashboard Status	Used but not fully featured
Person interviewed	Mr. Md. Mostakim First Assistant Vice President Finance & Account Division Al-Arafah Islam Bank Limited, Head Office, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Source: (Adapted from the website of Al-Arafah Islami Bank Limited, Accessed on 20.08.2022).

3.6 Standard Chartered Bangladesh

Standard Chartered Bank is the largest international bank in Bangladesh with 30 Branches & Booths and 87 ATMs; employing over 2,000 people. It is the only foreign bank in Bangladesh with a presence in 6 cities – Dhaka, Chittagong, Khulna, Sylhet, Bogra, and Narayanganj; including offshore banking units inside Dhaka Export Processing Zone (DEPZ) at Savar and Chittagong Export Processing Zone (CEPZ).

Name of the Company	Standard Chartered Bank Bangladesh
Company Type	Multinational Company
Head Office	67, Gulshan Avenue, Dhaka-1212, Bangladesh.
SWIFT	SCBLBDDX
Website	www.sc.com/bd/
CBS Status	Fully functional
Financial Dashboard Status	Used but not fully featured
Person interviewed	

Source: (Adapted from the website of Standard Chartered Bank Bangladesh, Accessed on 20.08.2022).

3.7 HSBC Bangladesh

HSBC (The Hong Kong and Shanghai Banking Corporation Ltd.) is one of the world's largest banking and financial services organizations. HSBC opened its first branch in Bangladesh in 1996. It offers a range of financial services in Bangladesh including commercial banking, consumer banking, payments, and cash management, trade services, treasury, and custody and clearing.

Name of the Company	HSBC Bank Bangladesh
Company type	Multinational Company
Head Office	Level 4, Shanta Western Tower 186 Bir Uttam Mir

	Shawkat Ali Road Tejgaon Industrial Area, Dhaka 1208.
SWIFT	HSBCBDDH
Website	www.hsbc.com.bd
CBS Status	Fully functional
Financial Dashboard Status	Used but not fully featured
Person interviewed	

Source: (Adapted from the website of HSBC Bank Bangladesh, Accessed on 20.08.2022).

3.8 NRB Commercial Bank Limited

A bank like NRB may play a vital role in achieving the desired goal. Besides, in the prevailing situation of Banking operations in Bangladesh, it is highly expected that the new bank shall be able to compete with the other banks by adopting new concepts of Risk Management and building up good Assets and Health of the organization. We believe in consideration of the above issues application for the desired bank was invited by Bangladesh Bank and LOI was issued on 2nd April 2013 in favor of eligible entrepreneurs.

Name of the Company	NRB Commercial Bank Limited
Company type	Private Limited Company
Head Office	114 Motijheel C/A , Dhaka-1000
SWIFT	NRBCBDDH
Website	www.nrbcommercialbank.com
CBS Status	Fully functional
Financial Dashboard Status	Used but not fully featured
Person interviewed	Mr. Md. Mosharraf Hossain Senior Executive Office & Head of Branch NRB Commercial Bank Limited, Khushtia Branch, Bangladesh

Source: (Adapted from the website of NRBC Bank, Accessed on 20.08.2022).

3.9 IFIC Bank Limited

International Finance Investment and Commerce Bank Limited (IFIC Bank) is a banking company incorporated in the People's Republic of Bangladesh with limited liability. It was set up at the instance of the Government in 1976 as a joint venture between the Government of Bangladesh and Sponsors in the private sector with the objective of working as a finance company within the country and setting up joint venture banks/financial institutions abroad. In 1983 when the Government allowed banks in the private sector, IFIC was converted into a full-fledged commercial bank. The Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh holds 32.75% of the share capital of the Bank. Sponsors/Directors having vast experience in the field of trade and commerce own 4.11% of the share capital and the rest is held by Institutions both local & foreign and General Shareholders. The Government is being represented by three nominated Directors on the Board of the Bank and as such, the present combined shareholding of the Sponsors/Directors are 36.86% of the total outstanding share capital of the Bank.

Name of the Company	IFIC Bank Limited
Company type	Private Limited Company
Head Office	IFIC Tower, 61 Purana Paltan, Dhaka-1000
SWIFT	IFICBDDH
Website	www.ificbank.com.bd
CBS Status	Fully functional
Financial Dashboard Status	Used but not fully featured
Person interviewed	Mr. Risal Md. Main Ud-Daula Senior Principal Officer & Manager Operations IFIC Bank Limited, Faridpur, Bangladesh

Source: (Adapted from the website of IFIC Bank Limited, Accessed on 20.08.2022).

3.10 The Premier Bank Limited

The Premier Bank Limited was incorporated in Bangladesh as a banking company on June 10, 1999, under the Companies Act.1994. Bangladesh Bank, the central bank of Bangladesh, issued banking license on June 17, 1999, under Banking Companies Act. of 1991. The Head Office of Premier Bank Limited is located at Banani, one of the main commercial and business areas of Dhaka city.

Name of the Company	The Premier Bank Limited
Company type	Private Limited Company
Head Office	IQBAL CENTRE, 42 Kemal Ataturk Avenue, Banani, Dhaka-1213
SWIFT	PRMRBDDH
Website	www.premierbankltd.com
CBS Status	Fully functional
Financial Dashboard Status	Used but not fully featured
Person interviewed	Mr. Syed Sabbir Ahmed Junior Assistant Vice President & Manager Operation The Premier Bank Limited, Khulna Branch, Bangladesh

Source: (Adapted from the website of Premier Bank Limited, Accessed on 20.08.2022).

3.11 Conclusion

By visiting the bank's website and interviewing the bank's employees, it has come the observation that almost every bank uses core Banking system (CBS) software to maintain their business operations. But the CBS features are transactional, not analytical at all. On the other hand, every bank has the desire to have a clean financial analytics dashboard which will help them better management of profitability.

CHAPTER FOUR

Financial Dashboard Application Design

4.1 Introduction

Web application design is an important stage when building a web application. It focuses on the look and feel of the web application. The design stage encompasses several different aspects, including web-application infrastructure design, database model design, user interface (UI), usability (UX), content production, graphic design, etc. In this chapter, the design process using unified modeling language (UML) and database design using entity relationship diagram (ERD) for the financial analytics web application has been briefly explained.

4.2 Designing System using Unified Modeling Language (UML)

The Unified Modeling Language (UML) is a visual modeling language for the architecture, design, and implementation of complex software systems both structurally and behaviorally. UML has applications beyond software development, such as process flow in manufacturing. UML diagrams describe the boundary, structure, and behavior of the system and the objects within it. Considering the importance of UML for web application development the following UML diagram has been designed to understand the process flow of the financial analytics dashboard.

4.3 Use Case model of the Financial Dashboard including use case specifications

For building the web-based financial analytical dashboard system the design elements for a system have been constructed that can be used to manage KPI, Deposit Products, Loan Products, Revenue elements, Expenditure attributes, etc. for the organization that is involved in the financial sector of Bangladesh. The name of the system that has been designed is the Financial Analytics Dashboard. The main activities of the organization are receiving deposits by selling different deposit products from a potential customer and lending the collected money to the pupil who has the necessity.

Fig: 4.1 Use Case Model of Financial Dashboard System

4.4 Class diagram of the Financial Dashboard system including realization methods

Considering the use case designed above a class diagram has been produced of the said financial analytics dashboard system. In this class model, it is assumed that the system admin will be liable for managing the KPI, Performance, Deposit, and Loan of the system by either entering a new indicator/element or updating the existing one. The system admin will also be liable for managing the user blog system. He will also view blog entries. On the other hand, the manager of the branch is only responsible for entering blog article data into the system and can view the business performance and other key performance indicators.

Fig: 4.2 Class Diagram

4.5 Sequence diagram realizing the Financial KPI flow System

To draw the sequence diagram that realized the 'New KPI Entry' use case, the sequence of steps carried out in the 'KPI Entry System'. At the very beginning, a user who is a system admin will refer to the KPI Entry functionality. The KPI entry functionality of the system admin will check whether the indicators are already in the system or not. If the indicator is not in the system, then the system admin will enter the new indicator into the system otherwise the system admin will update the indicator figure following the KPI update functionality. Before entering the indicator into the system, After the KPI is either entered or updated, the KPI view functionality will be called by the manager of the branch to view the current position of key performance indicators.

Fig: 4.3 Sequence Diagram

4.6 Activity diagram of the Manage KPI Information Use Case

To describes the 'Manage KPI Information' use case of the Financial Dashboard System an activity diagram has been produced. In the first step of the diagram, it has been identified whether the KPI already exists in the system or not. For managing a new KPI, a separate activity, "New KPI Entry," is performed. On the other hand, if a KPI exists, the system administrator can perform two different activities—update an existing KPI or delete an existing KPI. Hence, the system checks the type of operation desired based on which two separate activities can be performed—"Update KPI" or "Delete KPI".

Fig: 4.4 Activity Diagram of KPI Information Use Case

4.7 Use Case Realization (collaboration) Diagram of KPI Entry Use Case

To identify the classes that collaborate in the 'KPI Entry' use case, a realization (collaboration) diagram has been drawn. In this diagram, we mentioned that in the KPIEntry_UI boundary, the system admin will enter the all-new KPI and the data will be stored in the KPI entity where one system admin can enter unlimited KPI to the said table.

Fig: 4.5 Use Case Realisation (collaboration) Diagram of KPI entry

4.8 Use Case Realization (collaboration) Diagram of Performance Entry Use Case

To identify the classes that collaborate in the 'Performance Entry' use case, a realization (collaboration) diagram has been drawn. In this diagram, we mentioned that in the PerformanceEntry_UI boundary, the system admin will enter the all-new Performance item and the data will be stored in the Performance entity where one system admin can enter unlimited performance item to the said table.

Fig: 4.6 Use Case Realisation (collaboration) Diagram of Performance entry

4.9 Use Case Realization (collaboration) Diagram of Deposit Entry Use Case

To identify the classes that collaborate in the 'Deposit Entry' use case, a realization (collaboration) diagram has been drawn. In this diagram the DepositEntry_UI boundary, the system admin will enter the all-new deposit product and the data will be stored in the Deposit entity where one system admin can enter unlimited deposit items to the said table.

Fig: 4.7 Use Case Realisation (collaboration) Diagram of Deposit entry

4.10 Use Case Realization (collaboration) Diagram of Loan Entry Use Case

To identify the classes that collaborate in the 'Loan Entry' use case, a realization (collaboration) diagram has been drawn. In this diagram the LoanEntry_UI boundary, the system admin will enter the all-new Loan product and the data will be stored in the Loan entity where one system admin can enter unlimited loan products to the said table.

Fig: 4.8 Use Case Realisation (collaboration) Diagram of Loan entry

4.11 Use Case Realization (collaboration) Diagram of Blog Entry Use Case

To identify the classes that collaborate in the 'Blog Entry' use case, a realization (collaboration) diagram has been drawn. In this diagram, the BlogEntry_UI boundary, the system admin, as well as the manager of the branch, will enter and update the all-new blog article, and the data will be stored in the article entity where many users of the blog as well as the system admin can enter unlimited blog article to the said table.

Fig: 4.9 Use Case Realisation (collaboration) Diagram of Blog entry

4.12 Designing Entity Relationship Diagram (ERD)

Entity Relationship Diagram ER model is a type of structural diagram for use in database design. An ERD contains different symbols and connectors that visualize two important pieces of information: The major entities within the system scope, and the inter-relationships among these entities. So that the ERD is very essential for designing a database model. In this section, the ERD of the web-based financial analytical dashboard system has been designed considering the basic financial indicators. For the basic financial indicators, there are six entities have been taken into the consideration, such as KPI, Performance, Deposit, Loan, Revenue, Expenditure etc. For the blog elements articles and comments, entity has also been designed.

Fig: 4.10 Entity Relationship Diagram (ERD)

ERD Models for a new web-based Financial Analytical Dashboard

Rakib Uddin Ahmed | Student ID 30051154| August 22, 2022

ERD Cardinality

|| ————— ○
One (and only) to Many

○ ————— ○
Many to Many

—+ ————— ○
One to Many

KPI Entity: We have designed the KPI Entity and all its attributes for storing all the critical and analytical key performance indicators of the bank by which the branch managers and other stakeholders can identify critical and vulnerable indicators of the business and take prompt action on the issues.

Performance Entity: We have designed a Performance Entity and all its attributes for storing all the present business performance of the bank, by which the branch managers and top management of the bank can monitor the present business performance and can focus on profitability.

Deposit Entity: Deposit is the main blood flow for the banking business. That's why Deposit Entity has been designed for keeping records of different product-wise deposit positions, by which the management can closely monitor the individual product-wise deposit and set new deposit hunting targets.

Loan Entity: Loans and investments play the most vital role in the profitability of the banking industry. So that it is essential to preserve all the information on loans and investments. Thus, a Loan entity has been structured, by which the branch managers can monitor the loan and investment position of the bank and can take initiatives for increasing the profit.

Revenue Entity: We have designed Revenue Entity and all its attributes for storing all the elements which influence the revenue of the bank by which the branch managers can identify every element of revenue of the business and take prompt action on the issues.

Expense Entity: By reducing incurred expenses business organization can achieve desired target of profit. So that for storing expenses related information we have designed expense entity and all its attributes.

Article Entity: In this web application a blog writing apps has been introduced. By this blog apps managers and top management of the bank can discuss any issues of the business or can share any secret ideas securely in the same platform. Top management can also give message to the managers about any business changes or new business introduced. So that an article entity has been designed.

Comment Entity: We have designed comment Entity and all of its attributes because any one can comment on any particular articles or any critical business discussion.

4.13 Conclusion

Every web application or any other software is needed to the clean and concise design considering the key functionality of the system for implementation. To satisfy the requirements of the financial analytics dashboard, the architecture of the dashboard has been designed using unified modeling language (UML). Where the Use Case model of the financial dashboard system has been designed including use case specifications for constructing key functionality of the system. A Class diagram of the system has been drawn including realization methods to specify the main classes and its association. A Sequence diagram of a major functionality the dashboard system has been designed to demonstrate the sequence of steps carried out in the entry system of the application. An Activity diagram and some Collaboration diagram has also design to better understand the system. Moreover, the database design using entity relationship diagram (ERD) for the financial analytics web application has also been drawn to identify the relationship between the entity. This design would be helpful to implement the system more accurately.

CHAPTER FIVE

Financial Dashboard Implementation

5.1 Introduction

The main aim of the research is to build a web-based financial analytics dashboard for better management of profitability for bank and non-bank financial organizations in Bangladesh. To satisfy the main aim of the study, a web-based financial analytical dashboard application has been built. The web application consists of a client and server part, but the main program logic is located on the client side. The server part is mainly used for user authentication, which includes the list of indicators that must be retrieved as per requirements. The client side of the web application has been created using Python where Django is used for creating the web framework. Pandas, Matplotlib, Folium, NumPy, HTML5 CSS, Chart JS and other required libraries are used to analyze significant financial indicators, and ratios and visualize the information on the dashboard. In the following section the main frameworks, technologies, and web application building process has been briefly explained.

5.2 Python

For building the web application Python programming language has been used because this is the lesson learn language, as well as Python, has become one of the most popular programming languages in the world in recent years. It's used in everything from machine learning to building websites and software testing. It can be used by developers and non-developers alike. Python is a general-purpose language, which means it's designed to be used in a range of applications, including data science, software and web development, automation, and generally getting stuff done. Python is a computer programming language often used to build websites and software, automate tasks, and conduct data analysis. This versatility, along with its beginner-friendliness, has made it one of the most-used programming languages today. A survey conducted by industry analyst firm RedMonk found that it was the second-most popular programming language among developers in 2021 (What Is Python Used For?, 2022).

5.3 Django

For creating the web application, the Django web framework has been used. Because Django is a high-level Python web framework that enables rapid development of secure and maintainable websites. Built by experienced developers, Django takes care of much of the hassle of web development, so you can focus on writing your app without needing to reinvent the wheel. It is free and open source, has a thriving and active community, great documentation, and many options for free and paid-for support. It is versatile and can be (and has been) used to build almost any type of website — from content management systems and wikis, through to social networks and news sites.

It can work with any client-side framework and can deliver content in almost any format (including HTML, RSS feeds, JSON, and XML). Django is written in Python, which runs on many platforms. That means that you are not tied to any particular server platform and can run your applications on many flavors of Linux, Windows, and macOS. Furthermore, Django is well-supported by many web hosting providers, who often provide specific infrastructure and documentation for hosting Django sites (Django introduction - Learn web development | MDN, 2022).

5.4 Chart.js

Chart.js is an easy way to include animated, interactive graphs on your website for free. Chart.js is a free JavaScript library for making HTML-based charts. It is one of the simplest visualization libraries for JavaScript and comes with the many built-in chart types: Scatter Plot, Line Chart, Bar Chart, Pie Chart, Donut Chart, Bubble Chart, Area Chart, Radar Chart, Mixed Chart (Chart.js, 2022). In this web application, Chart.js has been used for visualizing key performance indicators of the organization by displaying many interactive charts.

5.5 SQLite3

SQLite is a C-language library that implements a small, fast, self-contained, high-reliability, full-featured, SQL database engine and it comes with python library. SQLite is the most used database engine in the world. SQLite is built into all mobile phones and most computers and comes bundled inside countless other applications that people use every day. The SQLite file format is stable, cross-platform, and backwards compatible and the developers pledge to keep it that way through the year 2050.

5.6 Web-Based Financial Analytics Dashboard Building Process

To mitigate the requirements of the objectives of the research a financial analytics dashboard web application has been developed. This application allows users to monitor, create, modify, and delete the key performance indicators of the business which influenced the business profitability. The homepage will list all major indicators and there will be a dedicated detail page for each individual element. Moreover, an analytical blog apps also has been included in this application for discussing important business issues in the forum. For creating the web application, the Django web framework has been used, and flowed the below-mentioned steps to build the application.

The steps for setting up a new Django project are as follows:

- create a new directory for our code on the Desktop called dashboard

- install Django in a new virtual environment
- create a new Django project called financial_dashboard
- create two separate new apps charts and article
- perform a migration to set up the database
- update settings.py

By executing the following code in a new command line console, the brand-new project and required apps have been created in Django and by navigating the localhost in the browser to <http://127.0.0.1:8000/> the project has been tested by successfully launched page.

Table-5.1: Code snippets for creating a new project in Django

Python code for creating new project
<pre> django-admin startproject financial_dashboard python manage.py startapp charts python manage.py startapp article python manage.py makemigrations charts python manage.py makemigrations article python manage.py migrate python manage.py runserver </pre>

Figure-5.1: Console Terminal on execution

```

C:\Windows\System32\cmd.exe - python manage.py runserver
Running migrations:
  Applying contenttypes.0001_initial... OK
  Applying auth.0001_initial... OK
  Applying admin.0001_initial... OK
  Applying admin.0002_logentry_remove_auto_add... OK
  Applying admin.0003_logentry_add_action_flag_choices... OK
  Applying contenttypes.0002_remove_content_type_name... OK
  Applying auth.0002_alter_permission_name_max_length... OK
  Applying auth.0003_alter_user_email_max_length... OK
  Applying auth.0004_alter_user_username_opts... OK
  Applying auth.0005_alter_user_last_login_null... OK
  Applying auth.0006_require_contenttypes_0002... OK
  Applying auth.0007_alter_validators_add_error_messages... OK
  Applying auth.0008_alter_user_username_max_length... OK
  Applying auth.0009_alter_user_last_name_max_length... OK
  Applying auth.0010_alter_group_name_max_length... OK
  Applying auth.0011_update_proxy_permissions... OK
  Applying auth.0012_alter_user_first_name_max_length... OK
  Applying sessions.0001_initial... OK

C:\Users\InfoSoft BD\Desktop\dashboard\financial_dashboard>python manage.py runserver
Watching for file changes with StatReloader
Performing system checks...

System check identified no issues (0 silenced).
August 31, 2022 - 14:55:16
Django version 4.0.5, using settings 'financial_dashboard.settings'
Starting development server at http://127.0.0.1:8000/
Quit the server with CTRL-BREAK.

```

Figure-5.2: Project launching in the browser

5.7 Database Models

What are the characteristics of a financial analytical dashboard application? In this case it has been assumed that each key performance indicators of the dashboard have a description and figure. That's why by populating the below code snippets the database model has been created through models.py.

Table-5.2: Code snippets for creating database model

Python code for creating database model:
<pre> from django.conf import settings from django.contrib.auth import get_user_model from django.db.models.fields import CharField, IntegerField, FloatField from django.db import models from django.urls import reverse class KPI(models.Model): description = models.CharField(max_length=200) amount = models.FloatField() date = models.DateTimeField(auto_now_add=True) author = models.ForeignKey(get_user_model(), on_delete=models.CASCADE, </pre>

```
)
def __str__(self):
    return f'{self.description} - {self.amount}'
def get_absolute_url(self):
    return reverse('kpi_detail', args=[str(self.id)])
class Performance(models.Model):
    description = models.CharField(max_length=200)
    amount = models.IntegerField()
    def __str__(self):
        return f'{self.description} - {self.amount}'
class Deposit(models.Model):
    description = models.CharField(max_length=200)
    amount = models.IntegerField()
    date = models.DateTimeField(auto_now_add=True)
    author = models.ForeignKey(
        get_user_model(),
        on_delete=models.CASCADE,
    )
    def __str__(self):
        return f'{self.description} - {self.amount}'
    def get_absolute_url(self):
        return reverse('deposit_detail', args=[str(self.id)])
class Loan(models.Model):
    description = models.CharField(max_length=200)
    amount = models.IntegerField()
    def __str__(self):
        return f'{self.description} - {self.amount}'
class Income(models.Model):
    description = models.CharField(max_length=200)
    amount = models.IntegerField()
    def __str__(self):
        return f'{self.description} - {self.amount}'
class Expense(models.Model):
    description = models.CharField(max_length=200)
    amount = models.IntegerField()
    def __str__(self):
        return f'{self.description} - {self.amount}'
```

In the above code the class `models` and a subclass of `models.Model` has been imported. Using this subclass functionality it is possible automatically have access to everything within `django.db.models.Models` and can add additional fields and methods as desired. Now the database model is complete, it is needed to create the necessary views, URLs, and templates so users can display the information on the web application.

5.8 URLs

The user of the dashboard wants to monitor the dashboards indicators on the homepage so, it is required to create a new `urls.py` file within our `charts` app and the following code is required in the `url.py` file to display the home page and its context.

Table-5.3: Code snippets for creating URLs

Python code for creating URLs:
<pre> from django.urls import path from . import views from .views import * from .views import (depositEdit, depositDelete, depositDetail, kpiEdit, kpiDelete, kpiDetail, positionView,) urlpatterns = [path('index/', views.index,name='index'), path('performance/', views.performanceEntry,name='performance'), path('deposit/', views.depositEntry,name='deposit'), path('kpi/', views.kpiEntry,name='kpi'), path('loan/', views.loanEntry,name='loan'), path('income/', views.incomeEntry,name='income'), path('expense/', views.expenseEntry,name='expense'), path('position/', views.positionView,name='positionView'), path('<int:pk>/depositedit/', depositEdit.as_view(), name='depositedit'), # new path('<int:pk>/depositdetail/', depositDetail.as_view(), </pre>

```

name='deposit_detail'), # new
    path('<int:pk>/ddepositdelete/', depositDelete.as_view(),
name='depositdelete'), # new
    path('<int:pk>/kpiedit/', kpiEdit.as_view(), name='kpiedit'),
    path('<int:pk>/kpidetail', kpiDetail.as_view(), name='kpi_detail'),
    path('<int:pk>/kpiddelete/', kpiDelete.as_view(), name='kpiddelete'),
    path('', views.home, name='home')
]

```

In the above code snippets, the views have been imported at the top and all the necessary URLs path has been declared. The empty string "" tells Python to match all values and make it a named URL, home.

5.9 Views

Now it is time to create the views for the web application. In the application, the class-based views have been used because it is excellent. By populating the following code the views of the web application have been created.

Table-5.4: Code snippets for creating Views

Python code for creating Views:

```

from django.shortcuts import render, redirect
from django.contrib.auth.mixins import LoginRequiredMixin
from django.core.exceptions import PermissionDenied
from django.views.generic import ListView, DetailView
from django.views.generic.edit import UpdateView, DeleteView, CreateView
from django.urls import reverse_lazy # new
from . forms import *
from .models import *
import pandas as pd

class kpiDetail(LoginRequiredMixin, DetailView):
    model = KPI
    template_name = 'forms/kpi_detail.html'
    login_url = 'login' # new

class kpiEdit(LoginRequiredMixin, UpdateView): # new
    model = KPI
    fields = ('description', 'amount',)
    template_name = 'forms/kpiedit.html'
    login_url = 'login' # new

```

```
def dispatch(self, request, *args, **kwargs): # new
    obj = self.get_object()
    if obj.author != self.request.user:
        raise PermissionDenied
    return super().dispatch(request, *args, **kwargs)

class kpiDelete(LoginRequiredMixin, DeleteView): # new
    model = KPI
    template_name = 'forms/kpidelete.html'
    success_url = reverse_lazy('kpi')
    login_url = 'login' # new

    def dispatch(self, request, *args, **kwargs): # new
        obj = self.get_object()
        if obj.author != self.request.user:
            raise PermissionDenied
        return super().dispatch(request, *args, **kwargs)

class depositDetail(LoginRequiredMixin, DetailView): # new
    model = Deposit
    template_name = 'forms/deposit_detail.html'
    login_url = 'login' # new

class depositEdit(LoginRequiredMixin, UpdateView): # new
    model = Deposit
    fields = ('description', 'amount',)
    template_name = 'forms/depositedit.html'
    login_url = 'login' # new

    def dispatch(self, request, *args, **kwargs): # new
        obj = self.get_object()
        if obj.author != self.request.user:
            raise PermissionDenied
        return super().dispatch(request, *args, **kwargs)

class depositDelete(LoginRequiredMixin, DeleteView): # new
    model = Deposit
    template_name = 'forms/depositdelete.html'
    success_url = reverse_lazy('deposit')
```

```
login_url = 'login' # new

def dispatch(self, request, *args, **kwargs): # new
    obj = self.get_object()
    if obj.author != self.request.user:
        raise PermissionDenied
    return super().dispatch(request, *args, **kwargs)

def home(request):
    deposits = Deposit.objects.all().values()
    loans = Loan.objects.all().values()
    incomes = Income.objects.all().values()
    expenses = Expense.objects.all().values()
    performances = Performance.objects.all().values()
    kpi = KPI.objects.all().values()

    dataPerformance=pd.DataFrame(performances)
    dataDeposit=pd.DataFrame(deposits)
    dataLoan=pd.DataFrame(loans)
    dataIncome=pd.DataFrame(incomes)
    dataExpense=pd.DataFrame(expenses)
    dataKpi=pd.DataFrame(kpi)

    labelPerformance=dataPerformance.description.tolist()
    figurePerformance=dataPerformance['amount'].tolist()
    labelDeposit=dataDeposit.description.tolist()
    figureDeposit=dataDeposit['amount'].tolist()
    labelLoan=dataLoan.description.tolist()
    figureLoan=dataLoan['amount'].tolist()
    labelIncome=dataIncome.description.tolist()
    figureIncome=dataIncome['amount'].tolist()
    labelExpense=dataExpense.description.tolist()
    figureExpense=dataExpense['amount'].tolist()
    labelKpi=dataKpi.description.tolist()
    figureKpi=dataKpi['amount'].tolist()

    mydict = {
        'labelPerformance':labelPerformance,
        'figurePerformance':figurePerformance,
        'labelDeposit':labelDeposit,
```

```
        'figureDeposit':figureDeposit,
        'labelLoan':labelLoan,
        'figureLoan':figureLoan,
        'labelIncome':labelIncome,
        'figureIncome':figureIncome,
        'labelExpense':labelExpense,
        'figureExpense':figureExpense,
        'labelKpi':labelKpi,
        'figureKpi':figureKpi
    }
    return render(request, 'index.html', context=mydict)
```

```
def positionView(request):
    deposits = Deposit.objects.all().values()
    loans = Loan.objects.all().values()
    incomes = Income.objects.all().values()
    expenses = Expense.objects.all().values()
    performances = Performance.objects.all().values()
    kpi = KPI.objects.all().values()

    dataPerformance=pd.DataFrame(performances)
    dataDeposit=pd.DataFrame(deposits)
    dataLoan=pd.DataFrame(loans)
    dataIncome=pd.DataFrame(incomes)
    dataExpense=pd.DataFrame(expenses)
    dataKpi=pd.DataFrame(kpi)

    labelPerformance=dataPerformance.description.tolist()
    figurePerformance=dataPerformance['amount'].tolist()
    labelDeposit=dataDeposit.description.tolist()
    figureDeposit=dataDeposit['amount'].tolist()
    labelLoan=dataLoan.description.tolist()
    figureLoan=dataLoan['amount'].tolist()
    labelIncome=dataIncome.description.tolist()
    figureIncome=dataIncome['amount'].tolist()
    labelExpense=dataExpense.description.tolist()
    figureExpense=dataExpense['amount'].tolist()
    labelKpi=dataKpi.description.tolist()
    figureKpi=dataKpi['amount'].tolist()
```

```
mydict = {
    'labelPerformance':labelPerformance,
    'figurePerformance':figurePerformance,
    'labelDeposit':labelDeposit,
    'figureDeposit':figureDeposit,
    'labelLoan':labelLoan,
    'figureLoan':figureLoan,
    'labelIncome':labelIncome,
    'figureIncome':figureIncome,
    'labelExpense':labelExpense,
    'figureExpense':figureExpense,
    'labelKpi':labelKpi,
    'figureKpi':figureKpi
}

return render(request, 'home.html', context=mydict)

def index(request):
    deposits = Deposit.objects.all().values()
    loans = Loan.objects.all().values()
    incomes = Income.objects.all().values()
    expenses = Expense.objects.all().values()
    performances = Performance.objects.all().values()

    dataPerformance=pd.DataFrame(performances)
    dataDeposit=pd.DataFrame(deposits)
    dataLoan=pd.DataFrame(loans)
    dataIncome=pd.DataFrame(incomes)
    dataExpense=pd.DataFrame(expenses)

    labelPerformance=dataPerformance.description.tolist()
    figurePerformance=dataPerformance['amount'].tolist()
    labelDeposit=dataDeposit.description.tolist()
    figureDeposit=dataDeposit['amount'].tolist()
    labelLoan=dataLoan.description.tolist()
    figureLoan=dataLoan['amount'].tolist()
    labelIncome=dataIncome.description.tolist()
    figureIncome=dataIncome['amount'].tolist()
    labelExpense=dataExpense.description.tolist()
    figureExpense=dataExpense['amount'].tolist()
```

```
mydict = {
    'labelPerformance':labelPerformance,
    'figurePerformance':figurePerformance,
    'labelDeposit':labelDeposit,
    'figureDeposit':figureDeposit,
    'labelLoan':labelLoan,
    'figureLoan':figureLoan,
    'labelIncome':labelIncome,
    'figureIncome':figureIncome,
    'labelExpense':labelExpense,
    'figureExpense':figureExpense
}
return render(request, 'forms/index.html', context=mydict)

def kpiEntry(request):
    kpis = KPI.objects.all()

    if request.method == 'POST':
        form = KpiForm(request.POST)
        if form.is_valid():
            form.save()
            return redirect('kpi')
    else:
        form = KpiForm()

    context = {
        "kpis": kpis,
        "form": form
    }

    return render(request, 'forms/kpientry.html', context)

def depositEntry(request):
    deposits = Deposit.objects.all()

    if request.method == 'POST':
        form = DepositForm(request.POST)
        if form.is_valid():
            form.save()
```

```
        return redirect('deposit')
    else:
        form = DepositForm()

    context = {
        "deposits": deposits,
        "form": form
    }

    return render(request, 'forms/depositentry.html', context)

def loanEntry(request):
    loans = Loan.objects.all()

    if request.method == 'POST':
        form = LoanForm(request.POST)
        if form.is_valid():
            form.save()
            return redirect('loan')
    else:
        form = LoanForm()

    context = {
        "loans": loans,
        "form": form
    }

    return render(request, 'forms/loanentry.html', context)

def incomeEntry(request):
    incomes = Income.objects.all()

    if request.method == 'POST':
        form = IncomeForm(request.POST)
        if form.is_valid():
            form.save()
            return redirect('income')
    else:
        form = IncomeForm()
```

```
context = {
    "incomes": incomes,
    "form": form
}

return render(request, 'forms/incomeentry.html', context)

def expenseEntry(request):
    expenses = Expense.objects.all()

    if request.method == 'POST':
        form = ExpenseForm(request.POST)
        if form.is_valid():
            form.save()
            return redirect('expense')
    else:
        form = ExpenseForm()

    context = {
        "expenses": expenses,
        "form": form
    }

    return render(request, 'forms/expenseentry.html', context)

def performanceEntry(request):
    performances = Performance.objects.all()

    if request.method == 'POST':
        form = PerformanceForm(request.POST)
        if form.is_valid():
            form.save()
            return redirect('performance')
    else:
        form = PerformanceForm()

    context = {
        "performances": performances,
        "form": form
    }
```

```
    return render(request, 'forms/performanceentry.html', context)

def position(request):
    item = Performance.objects.all().values()
    df=pd.DataFrame(item)
    df1=df.description.tolist()
    df=df['amount'].tolist()
    mydict = {
        'df':df,
        'df1':df1
    }
    return render(request, 'position.html', context=mydict)

def deposit(request):
    item = Deposit.objects.all().values()
    df=pd.DataFrame(item)
    df1=df.description.tolist()
    df=df['amount'].tolist()
    mydict = {
        'df':df,
        'df1':df1
    }
    return render(request, 'deposit.html', context=mydict)

def loan(request):
    item = Loan.objects.all().values()
    df=pd.DataFrame(item)
    df1=df.description.tolist()
    df=df['amount'].tolist()
    mydict = {
        'df':df,
        'df1':df1
    }
    return render(request, 'loan.html', context=mydict)

def income(request):
    item = Income.objects.all().values()
    df=pd.DataFrame(item)
```

```
df1=df.description.tolist()
df=df['amount'].tolist()
mydict = {
    'df':df,
    'df1':df1
}
return render(request, 'income.html', context=mydict)
def expense(request):
    item = Expense.objects.all().values()
    df=pd.DataFrame(item)
    df1=df.description.tolist()
    df=df['amount'].tolist()
    mydict = {
        'df':df,
        'df1':df1
    }
    return render(request, 'expense.html', context=mydict)
```

Here Django Templating Language has used to set up a simple for loop for each indicator's elements. It is also to be mentioned here that the contains all the objects in our view.

Now it's time to start the Django server again: "python manage.py runserver" and refresh <http://127.0.0.1:8000/> the system is running properly.

5.10 Navigation Page

For Building the web-based financial analytical dashboard, first of all, a website has been created using the Django web framework and HTML and CSS have been used for necessary styling. For accessing different indicators of the dashboard, a Navigation Page of the website has been created. This is the main home page of the dashboard system. The user of the dashboard can easily navigate or switch any of the pages through this navigation screen. The main navigation elements of this home page are log in and Sign Up. Any user of the dashboard needs to Login or Sign Up to the system to access the dashboard. That's why Login and Sign-Up button is placed on the top of the page in a navigation bar.

Figure-5.3: Home screen in the browser

Figure-5.4: Team details in browser

5.11 Sign-Up Page

For the security and authentication of the system Django user authentication model has been used. Any user of the dashboard needs to Login or Sign Up to the system to access the dashboard. That's why a Sign-Up page has been created. Users can sign up through this page by inserting user credentials.

Figure-5.5: Sign-Up Screen in browser

5.12 Login Page

As per the design of the system user Login is mandatory for accessing the dashboard. So, we have introduced a Login page. From this page, users can log in to the system as well as can maintain their user credentials by using Forgot Password option.

Figure-5.6: Login screen in the browser

5.13 Business Position Monitoring Page

After entering the system user of the dashboard can monitor the business position by simply navigating the position page. In this user can monitor the current business position, what is the deposit position? is the loan position of the bank increasing? are the KPI indicators in the right direction? is the expenditure needed to be curtailed? every parameter of the business can be monitored from here which is influenced the profitability by displaying interactive charts and figures.

Figure-5.7: Business position monitoring screen in the browser

Figure-5.8: Loan position monitoring screen in the browser

Figure-5.9: Deposit position monitoring screen in the browser

5.14 Indicator Page

By entering the indicator page user can view the current indicators, append new indicators, and modify the existing position of an indicator which is used to display the business position. This is the management part of the dashboard system. The manager and other users can view the position from here and the admin user can modify or add the indicator with prior consent from the authority.

Figure-5.10: Indicator position monitoring screen in the browser

Figure-5.11: Business position entry screen in browser

Figure-5.12: Deposit position entry screen in the browser

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `localhost:8000/deposit/`. The page is titled "Deposit Performance". On the left, there is a form titled "Add New Deposit Products" with fields for "Description:", "Amount:", and "Author:". Below the form is a "Save" button. To the right of the form is a line chart titled "Deposit Performance as on 30 June 2022". The chart shows the following data points:

Product Description	Figure
Current Deposit	66397
Savings Deposit	39518
Short Notice Deposit (SND)	46750
Fixed Deposit	128673
Deposit Scheme	44610
Bills Payable	
Others Deposit	

Below the chart is a table with the same data as above, including "Action" links for "Edit" and "Delete" for each product description.

Figure-5.13: Deposit position edit screen in the browser

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `localhost:8000/3/depositedit/`. The page is titled "Edit". At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for "Home", "Search", "Contact", "rakib", "Position", "Indicators", "Blogs", "Change password", and "Log Out". Below the navigation menu is a breadcrumb trail: "Home Performance Deposit Loan Income Expense". The main content area has a form titled "Edit" with fields for "Description*" (containing "Savings Deposit") and "Amount*" (containing "39518"). Below the form is an "Update" button.

5.15 Financial Analytical Blogs

A well-defined analytical blogs app has been included in the dashboard system. Through this blog, the management can circulate important instructions and business decisions guideline to the managers of the bank without sending individual e-mails to all managers separately. Even the manager's forum can discuss any business issues particularly case-to-case discussions and other greetings by accessing the blog system of the dashboard.

Figure-5.14: Financial blog screen in the browser

Figure-5.15: Financial blog posting screen in browser

5.16 Conclusion

Focusing on the main aim of the research the above web-based financial analytics dashboard has been built for better management of profitability for bank and non-bank financial organizations in Bangladesh. For creating the web application, the latest tools and technology have been used like Python and Django used for creating the web framework. Pandas, Matplotlib, Folium, NumPy, HTML5 CSS, Chart JS, and other popular libraries are used to analyze significant financial indicators, and ratios and visualize the information on the dashboard. The key content of the application is focused on entering the key performance indicator of the business into the system and visualizing the system through interactive charts, graphs, and other numerical forms, which might be helpful in taking decisions by analyzing the data on the dashboard.

CHAPTER SIX

Financial Analytics Dashboard Evaluation

6.1 Introduction

A recurrent challenge of many projects or any developments faces is to have a clear establishment of measurement and evaluation of a conceptual framework useful for quality assurance processes and programs. While many useful approaches for successful practical examples of evaluation and measurement programs exist, the inability to specify measurement and evaluation concepts clearly and consistently could unfortunately hamper the progress of the projects or developments. Nevertheless, any financial analytics dashboard web application required expert opinion on the KPIs and other features of the dashboard. Evaluation program—maybe as part of a measurement and analysis process area and quality assurance strategy. In this chapter, the financial analytics dashboard features evaluation process has been described.

6.2 Dashboard Evaluation Process

Together with three financial experts and existing personnel from the financial domain, a review of the financial dashboard was performed. The main goal was to examine the dashboard functionality and evaluate if the dashboard meets the needs of future users. The review took approximately half an hour to each evaluator and was conducted in an informal online interview. The financial experts were already familiar with the existing build dashboard application so not every interaction had to be explained in detail. The evaluation task has been performed through online chat. The review started with the default dashboard layout configuration which was suggested to be changed and adapted during the review. In the beginning, on the homepage, a cash flow monitoring feature should be included as opined by one of the evaluators. The overall task of the review was to examine the significant indicators and use the possibilities to construct more performance indicators. This should possibly be the feature of ratio analysis, data import feature from CBS, and some artificial intelligence features. After performing a task, the financial experts evaluated if the part of the dashboard functionality needed for this task was implemented in a way that is useful for future users. The fintech experts also asked questions from time to time during a task, which led to further discussions. Questions like "which formulation is used for the key performance indicators" or "how many indicators are included" were asked and discussed. This task was separated into further subtasks to show different aspects of the key performance indicators.

Some of the other tasks performed during the review were the assessment of the business performance by reviewing the indicators with the asset, liability, income, and expense. Furthermore, the possibility to customize the dashboard by changing the opined indicators and creating a different dashboard configuration for the other parameters. The interaction possibilities of the dashboard were

also discussed in general. The overall feedback of the domain experts for these tasks was that, they match the requirements and that they are now sufficient for the financial analytics dashboard. Besides, the review performed with the fintech experts, the overall performance of the dashboard application was tested. One requirement was that the dashboard application should be live trial for better assessment and for future requirements.

6.3 Conclusion

By reviewing the developed financial analytics dashboard, the fintech experts concluded with many valuable suggestions. As per the opinion of finance personnel, the built financial analytics dashboard functionality is currently serving the purpose of monitoring key performance indicators of Bank and non-bank financial organizations. They were amazed at the new blog functionality of the dashboard. On the other hand, they suggested onboarding some other functionality, which would be an addition in the financial sectors of Bangladesh.

CHAPTER SEVEN

Findings, Conclusion, and Recommendations

7.1 Introduction

From the mentioned literature review and based on secondary data collected from the organization's website and by interviewing the employees of the organizations, it is evident that the financial analytics dashboard plays a vital role in the finance sector of many developed countries in managing their profitability. On the other hand, it is being observed by researching every organization of financial sectors that are used in core banking system software for their daily transactional operations. But the software they are currently using is poorly featured and doesn't have the financial analytical ability. In this section, the summary of findings, limitations of the study, recommendations, and further scope of the study have been described.

7.2 Summary of Findings

- ✓ The results from the findings of the research show that the trend of using core banking system software and monitoring the financial indicators through the financial analytics dashboard of Bangladesh has improved to a large extent but there are some significant shortcomings.
- ✓ The research showed that there are some barriers named knowledge barriers, and management decision barriers to developing a financial dashboard in this sector to face the challenges.
- ✓ The development of the banking industry in the age of ICT is very much dependent on skilled IT vendors and there is a tremendous shortage of skilled IT Vendors in Bangladesh. Therefore, to face the challenges, the regulatory authorities should take proper initiatives.

7.3 Analyzing the present status and prospects regarding using Financial Dashboard in the banking sector of Bangladesh

This study showed that ICT embracement has got momentum in the last decade. Some first-mover banks in Bangladesh are in the process of CBS up-gradation, and some other banks are trying to implement CBS to improve competitiveness, operational efficiency, and regulatory compliance. Depending on the importance of CBS the central bank of Bangladesh issued circulars and guidelines for all scheduled banks of Bangladesh for implementing CBS in managing transactional activities. The CBS presently used in the Banking industries of Bangladesh are predominantly transactional. Some banks are trying to build financial analytics dashboards but those are not providing critical analytical financial, So The research has found that this is a high demand to build financial analytics dashboards for the betterment of bank and non-bank financial organizations in Bangladesh.

This study showed that there is a shining future for using financial analytics dashboards in Bangladesh. However, there are some challenges too. The main challenges are the negligence and lack of awareness among the management are liable for this condition. On the other hand, the shortage of skilled IT personnel and IT vendors are the main problems in building and implementing a financial dashboard in the banking sector in Bangladesh. limited trained human resources; improper use of technology; lack of technological knowledge, and implementation and monitoring of the Bank's information system are some other challenges in this sector.

7.4 Recommendations

Since the world is moving toward technology everything, so it should try to overcome all the barriers and try to develop such technology that is favorable for the development of financial analytical ability in the banking sector of Bangladesh. To continually improve the financial analytics ability the management should focus on developing the financial analytics dashboard which will help the manager and top management of the bank to monitor critical financial indicators and take the right decision.

For achieving the best possible results from the development of a financial analytical dashboard, some recommendations are as follows:

Infrastructure: Infrastructural barriers hinder the development of any technology-based banking activities. Therefore, the regulatory authorities and bank management should work together to improve the ICT infrastructure which fosters the development of financial analytics-based tools and technology in Bangladesh. The banks operating in this country also must invest sufficiently in the automation of their banking system.

Knowledge Gap: The management of the banking industry of Bangladesh is not aware of financial technology even though they are not interested in it, for decades ago. Therefore, the Bangladesh Bank along with the operating banks promotes knowledge about financial technology. Besides, some other initiatives should be taken for removing the knowledge barrier in this sector.

Management Issues: Efficient manpower is the main barrier to developing the financial analytics dashboard of Bangladesh. Provide adequate training and technical support to develop the manpower. An appropriate legal framework and proper infrastructure development are required.

Besides the above recommendations, some other issues should be considered for achieving an effective financial analytics dashboard in the banking sector of Bangladesh.

7.5 Limitation of the Study

It is common that every research has some limitations due to data collection, analysis, or interpreting the results. This study is not fully out of limitations. The researcher may choose methodology with which he is popular, but this method might not be appropriate for a particular study. However, to get accurate and concrete results from the research, the researcher tried hardly to avoid these limitations.

There are some limitations of this study. These limitations are given below:

- ✓ Constraint of time is one of the main limitations of this study. Such study needs much time for collecting necessary primary data.
- ✓ In addition, most of the banks in Bangladesh do not publish information regarding their cyber security or cyber threats.
- ✓ To assess the status of core banking system software and financial analytics dashboard system in Bangladesh properly more extensive study is essential.
- ✓ Limitations imposed on the statistical techniques are also applicable for the result of this study because of the use of statistical techniques.
- ✓ Moreover, news published on national dailies, articles published on different medias are not well justified. Therefore, there have a chance of presenting wrong information.

7.6 Scope for Further Research

The study has been conducted to analyze the present condition of using financial dashboard in the banking industry of Bangladesh and develop a web based financial analytics dashboard for better management of profitability for bank and non-bank financial organization of Bangladesh. For analyzing the present condition, some factors are considered that have influence over the overall banking system like infrastructure, legal system, and financial system. Besides those factors, many other factors also determine fortune of financial analytics dashboard in the banking industry of Bangladesh. Moreover, due to time, budget, and access constraints the research has been conducted based on secondary data which leads scope for further research. However, the research has done for analyzing the present conditions using financial analytics dashboard of banking industry of Bangladesh and developing a prototype financial indicator monitoring dashboard. Therefore, further research could be conducted for analyzing and showing other perspectives of financial indicator analysis dashboard in the banking industry of Bangladesh or other.

7.7 Conclusion

In this research, it has been observed very closely that, the banking sector of Bangladesh are struggling to achieve desired goal due to the non-availability of financial analytics information. Financial Data analytics has become an obvious part and parcel of many industries. The finance sector is no exception. Banks use analytics to identify the drawbacks, understand customer transaction patterns, and trace market trends for financial products and services. It helps understand and identify individual customer needs such as loans, insurance policies, and investments. It is assumed that financial analytics dashboard plays vital role in the finance sector of many developed countries towards managing their profitability. On the other hand, it is being observed by researching almost every organization of financial sectors are currently using core banking system software for their daily transactional operations. But the software they are currently using are poor featured and don't have the financial analytical feature. However financial analytics dashboard can act as a complementary towards banking sector in Bangladesh. Financial analytic dashboard can help to increase profit and reduced the incurred losses by making right decision at the right time. So, the research identified that, there is a scope of building financial analytics dashboard towards better management of profitability in the banking sector of Bangladesh.

Therefore, assuming the necessity of financial analytics dashboard in the development of banking sector of Bangladesh a well-defined web-based financial analytics dashboard has been developed considering many useful key performance indicators. For developing the dashboard, the lesson learn language Python has been used and Django has been used to creating the web framework.

The developed dashboard application is a unique tool for monitoring different financial indicators. The user can view the key performance indicators of bank which is influenced the profitability. The resulting insights can then be used to additionally perform a more detailed and specific analysis and verify established assumptions. During the evaluation of the dashboard application, some feedback from the organization's personnel has been collected for further development of the dashboard. However, not all creation steps are performed yet, as the dashboard is a prototype. The missing steps will be addressed during future developments after (further) user needs are identified using the dashboard prototype. For the future development of the application, it can be also considered to include a computational approach for detecting any missing indicators. Overall, a more advanced composite indicator creation mechanism can be implemented in the future.

CHAPTER EIGHT

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8.4 Appendixes:

8.4.1 Task Scheduler

The screenshot shows the ProjectLibre software interface. At the top, there is a menu bar with 'File', 'Task', 'Resource', and 'View'. Below the menu bar is a toolbar with various icons for views (Gantt, Network, WBS, Task Usage), zooming (Zoom In, Zoom Out), clipboard (Paste, Copy, Cut), and editing (Insert, Delete, Indent, Outdent, Link, Unlink). The main area displays a table with the following columns: Name, Work, Duration, Start, and Finish. The table contains 10 rows of tasks, each with a sub-row for the task name and a sub-row for the resource 'Rakib Uddin Ahmea'.

	Name	Work	Duration	Start	Finish
1	Brief Litarature Review	75 hours	9.375 days?	01/06/22 08:00	14/06/22 11:00
	<i>Rakib Uddin Ahmea</i>	<i>75 hours</i>	<i>9.375 days</i>	<i>01/06/22 08:00</i>	<i>14/06/22 11:00</i>
2	Data Collection	75 hours	9.375 days?	14/06/22 08:00	27/06/22 11:00
	<i>Rakib Uddin Ahmea</i>	<i>75 hours</i>	<i>9.375 days</i>	<i>14/06/22 08:00</i>	<i>27/06/22 11:00</i>
3	Problm Identify	25 hours	3.125 days?	27/06/22 08:00	30/06/22 09:00
	<i>Rakib Uddin Ahmea</i>	<i>25 hours</i>	<i>3.125 days</i>	<i>27/06/22 08:00</i>	<i>30/06/22 09:00</i>
4	System Analysis	25 hours	3.125 days?	30/06/22 08:00	05/07/22 09:00
	<i>Rakib Uddin Ahmea</i>	<i>25 hours</i>	<i>3.125 days</i>	<i>30/06/22 08:00</i>	<i>05/07/22 09:00</i>
5	ERD Design using UML	25 hours	3.125 days?	05/07/22 08:00	08/07/22 09:00
	<i>Rakib Uddin Ahmea</i>	<i>25 hours</i>	<i>3.125 days</i>	<i>05/07/22 08:00</i>	<i>08/07/22 09:00</i>
6	Database Structure Design ir	25 hours	3.125 days?	08/07/22 08:00	13/07/22 09:00
	<i>Rakib Uddin Ahmea</i>	<i>25 hours</i>	<i>3.125 days</i>	<i>08/07/22 08:00</i>	<i>13/07/22 09:00</i>
7	Web Application Developmer	200 hours	25 days?	13/07/22 08:00	16/08/22 17:00
	<i>Rakib Uddin Ahmea</i>	<i>200 hours</i>	<i>25 days</i>	<i>13/07/22 08:00</i>	<i>16/08/22 17:00</i>
8	Software Deployment and Te	25 hours	3.125 days?	16/08/22 08:00	19/08/22 09:00
	<i>Rakib Uddin Ahmea</i>	<i>25 hours</i>	<i>3.125 days</i>	<i>16/08/22 08:00</i>	<i>19/08/22 09:00</i>
9	Software Debuging	25 hours	3.125 days?	19/08/22 08:00	24/08/22 09:00
	<i>Rakib Uddin Ahmea</i>	<i>25 hours</i>	<i>3.125 days</i>	<i>19/08/22 08:00</i>	<i>24/08/22 09:00</i>
10	Report Writing	100 hours	12.5 days?	24/08/22 08:00	09/09/22 13:00
	<i>Rakib Uddin Ahmea</i>	<i>100 hours</i>	<i>12.5 days</i>	<i>24/08/22 08:00</i>	<i>09/09/22 13:00</i>

8.4.2 Time Schedule

		Name	Duration	Start	Finish	Predecessors
1		Brief Litarature Review	9.375 days?	01/06/22 08:00	14/06/22 11:00	
2		Data Collection	9.375 days?	14/06/22 08:00	27/06/22 11:00	
3		Problm Identify	3.125 days?	27/06/22 08:00	30/06/22 09:00	
4		System Analysis	3.125 days?	30/06/22 08:00	05/07/22 09:00	
5		ERD Design using UML	3.125 days?	05/07/22 08:00	08/07/22 09:00	
6		Database Structure Design in Oracle	3.125 days?	08/07/22 08:00	13/07/22 09:00	
7		Web Application Development in Pyt...	25 days?	13/07/22 08:00	16/08/22 17:00	
8		Software Deployment and Testing	3.125 days?	16/08/22 08:00	19/08/22 09:00	
9		Software Debuging	3.125 days?	19/08/22 08:00	24/08/22 09:00	
10		Report Writing	12.5 days?	24/08/22 08:00	09/09/22 13:00	

8.4.3 Gantt Chart

8.4.4 Resource Allocation

1 Rakib Uddin Ahmed				
Task ID	Task	Work	Assignment Units	Assign
2	Data Collection	75 hours		100%
1	Brief Litarature Review	75 hours		100%
3	Problm Identify	25 hours		100%
4	System Analysis	25 hours		100%
5	ERD Design using UML	25 hours		100%
6	Database Structure Design in	25 hours		100%
7	Web Application Development in	200 hours		100%
10	Report Writing	100 hours		100%
9	Software Debuging	25 hours		100%
8	Software Deployment and	25 hours		100%
		<u>600 hours</u>		

8.4.5 Art Artefact: Software Source Code

Financial Dashboard web application software source code and required library to run the system have been submitted separately into the Blackboard submission link. For developing the web application, pure Python code has been used and Django is used for creating the web framework. Pandas, Matplotlib, Folium, and NumPy library has used for creating the application, and these libraries are built-in inside the Python Package. HTML5, CSS, and Chart JS have been used for visualizing the dashboard application. For entering the system, the following credentials are required.

User ID: rakib

Password: Rakib@123

Server: localhost:8000

8.4.6 Transcript of Interview with Financial Expert

A video file named “Interview Meeting Recording.mp4” has been uploaded to the Blackboard submission link separately, as evidence of the expert opinion for the evaluation section.